

Azatriterpenes. Part-VIII. Synthesis of Ring-A Fused Pyrimidines of Pentacyclic Triterpenes[†]

R. PRASAD REDDY, A. RAVINDRANATH, B. SUDHAKAR, T. SUNDARA RAMAIAH*
and
M. VENKATESHWER RAO

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College (Osmania University), Hyderabad-500 001

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Condensation of urea, guanidine and thiourea with 2-formyl (hydroxymethylene) derivatives of methyl oleanonate (1), 11-oxomethyl oleanonate (2) and methyl betulonate (3) furnished their respective [3,2-*d*]pyrimidine-2'-ones (4-6), 2'-imino-[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines (7-9) and 2'-mercapto [3,2-*d*]pyrimidines (10-12). The compounds were characterised by their elemental and spectral data.

HETEROSTEROIDS, especially steroids fused with heterocyclic rings have been found to exhibit modified or accentuated activities¹. The fact that fusion of pyrimidine ring system to a number of steroidal hormones have modified their physiological activity²⁻⁵ prompted to synthesise ring-A fused pyrimidines of pentacyclic triterpenes as part of the scheme on azatriterpenes⁶.

In the present investigation 2-formyl (hydroxymethylene) derivatives of methyloleanonate (1)⁷, 11-oxomethyl oleanonate (2) and methylbetulonate (3)⁷ were condensed with urea, guanidine and thiourea. The condensation with urea had taken place in boiling ethylene glycol to afford the respective [3,2-*d*]pyrimidine-2'-ones (4-6) in 60% yield. The ir spectra of 4-6 showed bands at 1725 (ester C=O) and 1638 cm⁻¹ (C=O in the pyrimidine ring), and in the case of 11-oxo derivative at 1725, 1685 and 1635 cm⁻¹; λ_{max} (EtOH) 202 (67 200), 223 (72 500) and 312 nm (36 260). The elemental analysis and the spectral data confirm the proposed structures (4-6).

The condensation of 1-3 with guanidine and thiourea was smooth and had taken place in boiling ethanol to afford their respective 2'-imino[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines (7-9) and 2'-mercapto[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines (10-12) in good yields. The ir spectra of 7-9 showed bands at 1725 (ester C=O), 1638 (C=N stretch), 3200 (=NH stretch) and 3320 cm⁻¹ (for >N-H stretch). The ir spectra of 10-12 showed bands at 1725 (ester C=O) and 2580 cm⁻¹ (C-SH). The nmr spectra of the condensation products (10-12) had signals around δ 3.55 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 6.9 (1H, s, 6'-H) and 10.69 (1H, d, SH, D₂O exchangeable). From the above spectral data it can be concluded that the pyrimidine units in 10-12 were completely aromatised. The presence of SH group in 10-12 was further confirmed by

methylating with equimolar quantities of methyl iodide in dry acetone in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. The nmr spectra of the methylated products (13-15) showed a signal around δ 2.83 (3H, s) due to -S-CH₃ and no signal due to -S-H.

1; R-H,
2; R-O

3

4; R-H, R'-O
5; R-O, R'-O
7; R-H, R'-NH
8; R-O, R'-NH

6; R-O
9; R-NH

10; R-H, R'-H
11; R-O, R'-H
13; R-H, R'-CH₃
14; R-O, R'-CH₃

12; R-H
15; R-CH₃

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Experimental

The melting points were recorded using Biochem melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Nmr spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on a EM-360 (60 MHz) spectrometer with TMS as the internal standard, ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer Infracard 237 spectrophotometer and uv spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

Methyl-2-formyl(hydroxymethylene)olean-12-en-3,11-dione-28-oate (2): To methylolean-12-en-3,11-dione-28-oate (2 g) in dry benzene (25 ml), freshly distilled dimethyl formamide (5 ml), freshly distilled ethyl formate (5 ml) and sodium methoxide solution (25 ml prepared from 5 g of sodium) were added and refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, acidified and extracted with ether. The dried ether extract furnished the 2-formyl (hydroxymethylene) derivative (2) as colourless solid (1.5 g) which was crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 210–15° (Found: C, 76.1; H, 9.15. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_8$ requires: C, 75.29; H, 9.02%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3160 (chelated OH) and 1680 cm^{-1} (CHO); λ_{max} (EtOH) 287 nm, underwent a bathochromic shift of 20 nm in base (EtOH-0.1 N NaOH); δ 8.65 (1H, s, CHO)

Condensation of urea with β -keto aldehyde of pentacyclic triterpenes (1–3) Isolation of the [3,2-d]pyrimidine-2'-ones (4–6). A typical experiment: A solution of the triterpene β -keto aldehyde (1 g) and urea (500 mg) in ethylene glycol (50 ml; freshly distilled over KOH pellets) was refluxed for 12 h in an oil-bath and diluted with water. It was then extracted with ether and the ether extract washed several times with water. The residue obtained on removal of the solvent was adsorbed over a column of silica gel (50 g; < 200 mesh) and eluted with benzene (500 ml) and benzene-chloroform (1:1, 500 ml). The benzene eluate did not yield any residue. The benzene-chloroform eluate yielded [3,2-d]pyrimidine-2'-one (550 mg), which was crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles.

Methylolean-12-en[3,2-d]pyrimidine-2'-one-28-oate (4): It showed m.p. 130–35° (Found: C, 76.62; H, 9.04; N, 5.15. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8$ requires: C, 76.15; H, 9.23; N, 5.38%); ν_{max} 1720 (ester C=O) and 1640 cm^{-1} (C=O of pyrimidine ring); λ_{max} (EtOH) 205 (ϵ 67 200), 233 (72 000) and 315 nm (35 206).

Methylolean-12-en[3,2-d]pyrimidine-2'-11-dione-28-oate (5): It showed m.p. 165–68° (Found: C, 74.57; H, 8.12; N, 5.05. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 74.16; H, 8.61; N, 5.24%); ν_{max} 1725 (ester C=O), 1685 (11-keto), 1640 cm^{-1} (C=O of pyrimidine ring); λ_{max} (EtOH) 202 (ϵ 67 200), 230 (72 080) and 310 nm (35 250).

Methyl lup-20 (29)-en-[3,2-d]pyrimidine-2'-one-28-oate (6): It showed m.p. 146–48° (Found: C, 76.74; H, 8.89; N, 5.12. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8$ requires: C, 76.15; H, 9.23; N, 5.38%); ν_{max} 1730 (ester C=O) and 1635 cm^{-1} (C=O of pyrimidine ring);

λ_{max} (EtOH) 200 (ϵ 67 210), 215 (73 000) and 308 nm (35 280).

Condensation of guanidine/thiourea with β -keto aldehyde of pentacyclic triterpenes (1–3). Isolation of 2'-imino[3,2-d]pyrimidines (7–9)/2'-mercapto[3,2-d]pyrimidines (10–12): A solution of the triterpene β -keto aldehyde (800 mg) and guanidine hydrochloride (200 mg)–sodium acetate (200 mg)/thiourea in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 12 h and then poured into ice-cold water (200 ml). It was extracted with ether, the ether extract washed several times with water and the dried ether extract on removal of the solvent afforded 2'-imino[3,2-d]pyrimidine/2'-mercapto[3,2-d]pyrimidine, which was crystallised from CHCl_3 –MeOH as colourless needles.

Methylolean-12-en-2'-imino[3,2-d]pyrimidine-28-oate (7): It showed m.p. 165–70° (Found: C, 76.96; H, 9.17; N, 7.72. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_3\text{O}_8$ requires: C, 76.30; H, 9.44; N, 8.09%); ν_{max} 1720 (ester C=O), 1635 (>C=N), 3200 (=N–H) and 3220 cm^{-1} (>NH).

Methylolean-11-oxo-12-en-2'-imino[3,2-d]pyrimidine-28-oate (8): It showed m.p. 185–88° (Found: C, 74.55; H, 8.21; N, 7.52. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_3\text{O}_8$ requires: C, 74.30; H, 8.82; N, 7.88%); ν_{max} 1722 (ester C=O), 1685 (11-keto), 1633 (>C=N), 3210 (=NH) and 3220 cm^{-1} (>NH).

Methyl lup-20 (29)-en-2'-imino[3,2-d]pyrimidine-28-oate (9): It showed m.p. 172–75° (Found: C, 76.88; H, 9.03; N, 7.92. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_3\text{O}_8$ requires: C, 76.30; H, 9.44; N, 8.09%); ν_{max} 1730 (ester C=O), 1640 (>C=N), 3200 (=N–H) and 3205 cm^{-1} (>NH).

Methylolean-12-en-2'-mercapto[3,2-d]pyrimidine-28-oate (10): It showed m.p. 165–70° (Found: C, 74.45; H, 8.01; N, 4.82; S, 5.63. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_2\text{SO}_8$ requires: C, 73.88; H, 8.96; N, 5.22; S, 5.97%); ν_{max} 1725 (ester C=O) and 2585 cm^{-1} (C–SH); δ 3.54 (3H, s for COOCH_3), 5.28 (1H, t, CH=C), 6.8 (1H, s, 6'-H) and 10.72 (1H, d for SH).

Methylolean-11-oxo-12-en-2'-mercapto[3,2-d]pyrimidine-28-oate (11): It showed m.p. 195–99° (Found: C, 72.06; H, 8.25; N, 4.85; S, 5.56. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_2\text{SO}_8$ requires: C, 72.00; H, 8.36; N, 5.09; S, 5.82%); ν_{max} 1720 (ester C=O), 1685 (11-keto), 2580 cm^{-1} (C–SH); δ 3.52 (3H, s, COOCH_3), 5.31 (1H, s, HC=C), 6.2 (1H, s, 6'-H) and 10.51 (1H, d, SH).

Methyl lup-20(29)-en-2'-mercapto[3,2-d]pyrimidine-28-oate (12): It showed m.p. 157–60° (Found: C, 74.32; H, 8.35; N, 5.02; S, 5.92. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_2\text{SO}_8$ requires: C, 73.88; H, 8.96; N, 5.22; S, 5.97%); ν_{max} 1727 (ester C=O) and 2583 cm^{-1} (C–SH); δ 3.57 (3H, s, COOCH_3), 4.72 (2H, d, C=CH₂), 7.1 (1H, s, 6'-H) and 10.65 (1H, d, SH).

Methylation of 2'-mercapto[3,2-d]pyrimidines (10–12). Isolation of 2'-methylthio[3,2-d]pyrimidines (13–15): To a solution of 2'-mercapto[3,2-d]pyri-

midine (700 mg) in dry acetone (50 ml), fused potassium carbonate (2 g) and methyl iodide (0.3 ml) were added and refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. It was then cooled, filtered and on removal of acetone the methylated product was obtained as dark brown solid (700 mg), which was adsorbed over a column of silica gel (40 g, <200 mesh) and eluted with benzene and chloroform successively. The benzene eluate furnished a dark brown semi-solid (50 mg) which resisted further purification. The chloroform eluate furnished 2'-methylthio-[3,2-d]pyrimidine as a pale yellow solid (600 mg) which was crystallised from petroleum ether as pale yellow prisms.

Methylolan-12-en-2'-methylthio[3,2-d]pyrimidine-28-oate (13): It showed m.p. 210–12° (Found: C, 74.82; H, 9.12; N, 5.02; S, 5.83. $C_{34}H_{50}N_2SO_8$ requires: C, 74.18; H, 9.09; N, 5.09; S, 5.81%); δ 2.82 (3H, s, S-CH₃), 3.66 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.35 (1H, t, -CH=C<) and 6.9 (1H, s, 6'-H).

Methylolan-11-oxo-12-en-2'-methyl thio[3,2-d]pyrimidine-28-oate (14): It showed m.p. 245–48° (Found: C, 72.89; H, 8.42; N, 4.85; S, 5.63. $C_{34}H_{48}N_2SO_8$ requires: C, 72.76; H, 8.51; N, 4.96; S, 5.67%); δ 2.81 (3H, s, S-CH₃), 3.68 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.39 (1H, s, -CH=CK) and 6.52 (1H, s, 6'-H).

Methyl lup-20 (29)-en-2'-methyl thio-[3,2-d]pyrimidine-28-oate (15): It showed m.p. 250–55°

(Found: C, 74.21; H, 8.13; N, 4.82; S, 5.63. $C_{34}H_{50}N_2SO_8$ requires: C, 74.18; H, 9.09; N, 5.09; S, 5.81%); δ 2.85 (3H, s, S-CH₃), 3.69 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.70 (2H, d, HC=CH₂) and 7.0 (1H, s, 6'-H).

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